

INFLUENCE OF DIPLOMACY TO LANGUAGE CHANGE

Sevara Kurbanova: Andizhan State Foreign Language Institution

Mahmudova Gulshoda: Andizhan State Foreign Language Institution

Annotation: This research is an overview of strategies and techniques used in teaching the advanced ESP students of International relations a course of the Language of Diplomacy. The findings are based on the practical experience of the author as a co-ordinator of ESP undergraduate programmes and focus on the description of the linguo-didactic dominants at the core of the Language of diplomacy course. The aim of the course is to help students develop linguistic skills which are essential for effective presentation, persuasion and negotiation.

Key words: Diplomatic, Communication, Language, Technology, Negotiation

Being diplomatic involves using phrases to soften our statements when we deliver bad news or negative judgments. The use of these softening phrases conveys an awareness that our judgments are not necessarily right.¹

It has often been said that language is not only an instrument of communication, but the very essence of diplomacy. Diplomats engage in negotiations, persuasion, presentation, and communication, all of which necessitate language skills for the effective conduct of diplomatic work.

Both the written and the spoken language require the mastering of concepts and skills, and need to consider message and context. Language can also serve as a

form of action: when we warn, threaten, promise, suggest, agree, advise or otherwise, we are doing something, and not merely saying something. The role of the unsaid in communication (the meaningful silence) is equally crucial.

Language is as much important today as it was to the first envoys and negotiators. Today, technology is continuously shaping certain aspects of language and diplomacy, with the introduction of new tools for communication and interpretation, novel ways of capturing and preserving diplomatic documents, and methods that facilitate online negotiations. Despite the changes, core issues remain fundamental to the practice of diplomacy.ⁱⁱ

Language in diplomacy

An old and funny catchphrase says that one should use many languages to be properly understood: speaking to God, Latin; to the military, German; to the merchants, Greek and Arabic; to the musicians, Italian; to his cook, Chinese; to the sailors and engineers, English; to the artists, Russian; to friends, Spanish; to enemies Dutch or Hungarian; to his girl-friend, French; to his wife, Japanese...

What language should one use when speaking to diplomats, or what language should diplomats use? Or, to be more precise, what language/languages should a (young) diplomat try to learn to be more successful in his profession?

The term “language in diplomacy” obviously can be interpreted in several ways. First, as tongue (“mother” tongue or an acquired one), the speech “used by one nation, tribe, or other similar large group of people”;¹ in this sense we can say, for example, that French used to be the predominant diplomatic language in the first

half of the 20th century. Second, as a special way of expressing the subtle needs of the diplomatic profession; in this way it can be said, for example, that the delegate of such-and-such a country spoke of the given subject in totally non-diplomatic language. Also, the term can refer to the particular form, style, manner or tone of expression; such as the minister formulated his conditions in unusually strong language. It may mean as well the verbal or non-verbal expression of thoughts or feelings: sending the gunships is a language that everybody understands.

All of these meanings – and probably several others – can be utilised in both oral and written practice. In any of these senses, the use of language in diplomacy is of major importance, since language is not a simple tool, vehicle for transmission of thoughts, or instrument of communication, but very often the very essence of the diplomatic vocation, and that has been so from the early beginnings of our profession. That is why from early times the first envoys of the Egyptian pharaohs, Roman legates, mediaeval Dubrovnik consuls, etc., had to be educated and trained people, well-spoken and polyglots.ⁱⁱⁱ

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Communication between diplomats is a two-way street. One cannot expect to obtain information unless one is able and willing to convey useful information as well.

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It is first and foremost the act of sharing. The emphasis is normally on "what to say" rather than "what not to say". Sometimes, silence is more eloquent than words.

Trained diplomats avoid potentially aggressive, insensitive, offensive or destructive language. The diplomatic language is peace-making, peace-building and peace-promoting. Not only must diplomatic language be polite, choice of words must also be correct.

However, if one wishes to camouflage one's thoughts, it can be achieved by using a more complicated style, complex sentences, digressions, interrupting the other's flow of thought and introducing new topics. Ambiguity is a useful tool in diplomacy as it is in abstract art.

Today, English, French, Russian, Chinese, Spanish and Arabic are the official working languages at the United Nations. The best interpreters in the world are found at the UN, where speeches are interpreted live and written documents translated swiftly.

All other languages require the use of one's own interpreter who must be able to converse in the UN languages. When negotiations are conducted in smaller groups, no interpreters are present and the only medium of communication is English^{iv}

How to use diplomatic English in meetings is a challenge for native speakers and

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Explanation:

- this is direct with no apology for giving bad news. It can sound harsh with little empathy for the other person.
- softeners come at the beginning of the sentence and prepares your listener for the bad news you are giving them.^v

Reference

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ⁱⁱⁱ <https://www.diplomacy.edu/resource/use-of-language-in-diplomacy/>

^{iv} https://www-nst-com-my.cdn.ampproject.org/v/s/www.nst.com.my/amp/opinion/columnists/2022/03/775741/importance-language-diplomacy?amp_gsa=1&_js_v=a9&usqp=mq331AQIUAKwASCAAgM%3D#amp_tf=Manba%3A%20%251%24s&aoh=16819631966289&referrer=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com&share=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.nst.com.my%2Fopinion%2Fcolumnists%2F2022%2F03%2F775741%2Fimportance-language-diplomacy

^v <https://www.englishtco.com/how-to-use-diplomatic-english-in-meetings/>